

The dynamics of customer loyalty in B2C: understanding the buyer-seller relationship chain

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Abstract—This research aims to understand the relational mechanisms that shape customer loyalty in the B2C context by validating the mediating role of relational quality. A mixed approach was used: an exploratory qualitative study conducted among consumers initially identified the salient dimensions of relational quality, which served as the basis for constructing a sequential relational model that was quantitatively tested on a sample of 135 customers in different sectors of activity. The results based on structural equation modelling (Past Least Square) validate the arrangement of the facets of relational quality identified with buyer satisfaction and loyalty towards the seller to form a cumulative relational chain inherent to the buyer-seller dyad in the B2C context. Our conclusions contribute to enriching the theoretical framework of relational selling. The study provides managerial implications that reinforce the relational practices of salespeople.

Keywords: Relationship quality - Satisfaction - Loyalty, relationship chain, PLS

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's increasingly competitive B-to-C environment, we are witnessing the emergence of the relational approach (Sheth and Parvatiyar, 1995; Pellat et al., 2010). This translates into an evolution in sales and a renewal of processes, practices, and concepts (Aurier et al., 2001) and a transformation of the sales role (Bergadaâ, 1997), which is widely recognized in various areas as playing a key role in creating and maintaining quality customer relationships (Poujol, 2008; Crosby et al., 1990). Furthermore, this orientation considers customer loyalty as a major challenge and a guarantee of prosperity and competitive advantage (Petzer & Van Tonder, 2019; Arslan, 2020; Daulay et al., 2024). Customer loyalty cannot be reduced to simple repetitive behavior but is more accurately described as the result of a complex series of relationships (Mornay and Vernon, 2025). Therefore, identifying its determinants is crucial given its impact on customer retention, behavioral intentions, business growth, etc. (Wan et al., 2021). If satisfaction is usually the starting point for this customer loyalty process (Oliver, 1999), the relationship between satisfaction and loyalty is becoming increasingly fragile, particularly due to changing consumer demands (Kamath et al., 2020; Moliner-Tena et al., 2018). Indeed, despite the noted effect of satisfaction on loyalty (Hossain et al., 2021; Islam et al., 2021), it no longer guarantees customer retention on its own, which seems to depend more on other emotional and relational factors (Ghorbanzadeh & Rahegh, 2020; Sharma et al., 2020).

Considering these findings, it is necessary to understand the intermediate variables and their interrelationships (Boonlertvanich, 2019; Garepasha et al., 2021), including relational quality, which is generally reflected in trust and commitment (Morgan and Hunt, 1994) and which must be reevaluated considering broader dimensions (De Wulf et al., 2001). This thus plays a major mediating role that may confirm that loyalty stems from a gradual relational process (Budur and Poturak, 2021; Fusva et al., 2020).

However, despite the importance of this extended relational chain, existing research remains limited. Some “relational chains” have been proposed in specific contexts, such as the consumer-brand relationship and the relationship with the retail brand (Aurier et al., 2001; Kaabachi, 2007; Kim et al., 2015; Kamran-Disfani et al., 2017).

Although these sequences have been validated in various contexts, some of them suffer from certain shortcomings, such as a simplistic view of the relationship (Aurier et al., 2001). Moreover, the sequences proposed in the research are not universal. They depend on the sector, the type of service, the nature of customer experience, and cultural expectations (Palmatier et al., 2006).

Few studies truly analyze how satisfaction feeds into multidimensional relationship quality and how the latter leads to loyalty. To our knowledge, no research has proposed a relational chain inherent to the buyer-seller dyad in the B2C context.

Accordingly, this research aims to integrate the relational approach into the study of customer loyalty toward the seller and will seek to construct and validate a relational chain specific to the buyer-seller dyad in B2C that focuses on relational quality. Indeed, the B2C sector could, in turn, benefit from the attention paid to relationship development (Dwyer et al., 1987; Sheth and Parvatiyar, 1995). This raises a key question: *How does satisfaction, by feeding into the various dimensions of relationship quality, consolidate loyalty in B2C buyer-seller relationships, and in what way is the adoption of a relational sequence an essential tool in such a market?*

To answer this question, this research uses a mixed approach. First, a theoretical framework combined with an exploratory qualitative study on the concept of relational quality is used to identify its salient aspects in the context under study. Next, by interacting with other relational variables, these different components lead us to propose a research model and formulate hypotheses. An overview of the methodology applied to the study is then presented, followed by the results, managerial implications, limitations, and future directions for further research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

II.1. THE BUYER-SELLER RELATIONSHIP QUALITY: A CORE CONCEPT IN RELATIONSHIP MARKETING

Since Berry's (1983) and Grönroos' (1994) pioneering work, relationship marketing has been one of the dominant paradigms in marketing research. It proposes that commercial performance goes beyond simple one-off transactions to reflect the ability to develop a lasting and mutually beneficial relationship with the co-exchanger. In this context, relationship quality plays a crucial role in exchange relationships in a wide variety of contexts (services, tourism, B2B, digital environment), particularly in the B2C context, where the study of relational dynamics is essential given the role of emotions in the consumer experience, the increased power of customers, the proliferation of touch-points, asymmetric information, perceived risk, etc. (Lee and Kwon, 2011; Elshaer et al., 2025). It is defined as the perceived holistic strength of the relationship between exchange partners (Kumar et al., 1995; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2002). Numerous studies converge on three main components, namely satisfaction, trust, and commitment (Crosby et al., 1990; Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Qin et al., 2009; Walsh et al., 2010).

However, we note a lack of consensus regarding its multidimensional conceptualization (Qin et al., 2009). Current research highlights that this conceptualization can vary depending on the context, the sector, and consumers' specific expectations (Hennig-Thurau, 2000). This warrants the use of a preliminary qualitative approach to determine, within the B2C context, the dimensions that consumers use in their assessment of the quality of their relationship with the seller.

We opted to conduct in-depth interviews with ten consumers with diverse profiles in terms of age, gender, and socio-professional category (civil servant, unemployed, executive, etc.). The sample size was determined using the saturation criterion (Drapeau, 2004). The interviews focused on a series of open-ended questions addressed to the respondents.

To enhance the external validity of this research (Evrard et al., 2009), two different analyses were applied to the collected discourse: a thematic analysis completed by a lexical analysis (Lebart and Salem, 1994) using Lexico3 software. The findings reveal the preeminence of customer trust in the salesperson, the customer's emotional commitment, and the relationship's utility value in assessing the quality of the exchange relationship.

II.1.1. TRUST IN THE SALESPERSON

Based on the respondents' discourse, we note the emergence of trust in the exchange partner as the most important facet of a quality relationship (46.4%), with two aspects being mentioned most frequently: trust in the partner's goodwill and trust in their honesty. This seems legitimate to us. In fact, this concept is a key element of the relationship marketing paradigm (Wong and Sohal 2002). It reflects the minimization of uncertainty and vulnerability (Berry, 1995), as well as the minimization of

opportunistic behavior (Smith and Barclay, 1997). It is understood by several researchers as a major determinant of relationship success and maintenance and buyer loyalty (Dwyer et al., 1987; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2002; Roman, 2003).

II.I.II. CUSTOMER EMOTIONAL COMMITMENT

Commitment occupies a central place in relationship marketing literature (Garbarino and Johnson, 1999; Pritchard et al., 1999). It is characterized by the emotional bond established between a customer and their partner (Karim et al., 2023). It is centered on elements such as emotional attachment, overall satisfaction, and a sense of belonging and affiliation with the partner (Giovanis et al., 2015).

It's clear that customers' assessment of the quality of their exchange relationships revolves around their emotional attachment to the salesperson, thus referring to the emotional component of commitment and excluding the temporal and cognitive dimensions, which reflect opportunistic behavior and a quest for interesting alternatives (Volle and Mimouni, 2003).

II.I.III. UTILITARIAN VALUE OF THE RELATIONSHIP

The value of the relationship is a key element in relationship marketing literature as it promotes relationship development and maintenance (Ravald and Grönroos, 1996) and stems from the comparison between the benefits received and the sacrifices made in the relationship (Zeithaml, 1998). In terms of its multidimensional structure, which combines utilitarian, hedonic, and symbolic benefits (Volle and Mimouni, 2003), analysis of the verbatim data shows that the utilitarian value of the relationship is a key indicator of a good relationship between the seller and their customers. This refers to the rationality and objectivity of the consumer (Charfi and Volle, 2011) and “serves to maximize gains and minimize losses” (N'Goala, 2000, p.144). Although less prevalent than other dimensions of relationship quality (18.2%), the importance of this dimension for customers reflects the primacy of economic aspects in establishing the exchange relationship (Sanzo et al., 2003; Holmlund, 2008). Therefore, considering these analyses, we can comment on the first hypothesis, which is as follows:

H1: Relationship quality is a multidimensional construct, reflecting the utilitarian value of the relationship, trust, and emotional commitment to the exchange partner.

II.II. CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY: TOWARDS A RELATIONAL SEQUENCE MODEL

Loyalty is a driver of competitive advantage and a key factor in the survival, growth, and success of businesses (Palmatier et al., 2006; Petzer and Van Tonder, 2019). In arguing for its relational conceptualization, we define buyer loyalty to the seller as “the commitment and intention to continue dealing with a particular sales associate” (Reynolds and Arnolds, 2000, p.92). The analysis of interpersonal or organizational relationships in various contexts reveals that the sequential dynamics converging towards loyalty are often conceptualized in the form of a relational chain, such as in the B2B domain (Dwyer et al., 1987; Morgan and Hunt, 1994), public or administrative services (Tyler and Blader, 2013), healthcare (Thom et al, 2004), and digital environments (Gefen, 2002; Ahmed et al, 2021; Hsu et al, 2021; Magatef et al, 2023). These relational chains are based on certain theories used in relationship marketing, particularly social exchange theory (Blau, 1964), which offers an explanatory framework for understanding exchange relationships. According to this theory, partners continually evaluate the costs and benefits associated with their relationship, and the sustainability of a relationship depends on its ability to generate both social and economic benefits for all parties (Hsieh et al., 2019; Thomas and Gupta, 2021).

In the customer-seller relationship, this perspective is consistent with the sequential dynamics linking satisfaction, relationship quality, and loyalty, emphasizing that these constructs are part of a cumulative process of evaluating relationship benefits. Furthermore, Morgan and Hunt (1994) offer a particularly relevant framework for explaining the chain of relational variables through their theory of trust and commitment, according to which trust, commitment, and the sense of partnership that are directly linked to loyalty are nourished by satisfaction. Furthermore, approaches based on perceived fairness (Tax et al., 1998) emphasize that the way in which the customer is treated influences their perception of the relationship and their intention to maintain it.

In the B2C context, these theoretical mechanisms take on a specific aspect. Satisfaction is a crucial concept for understanding the dynamics of exchanges in relational transactions (Indriastuti and Hidayat, 2021). It involves a process of evaluating the

purchasing and consumption experience associated with a product or service within a given time frame (Suharto and Yuliansyah, 2023). Rather than a simple transactional evaluation, satisfaction has been operationalized in this study as an overall, cumulative evaluation of the exchange partner. This is an important precursor to customer loyalty (Supriyanto et al., 2021; Dam and Dam, 2021; Petzer and Roberts-Lombard, 2021; Prasetyo et al., 2021).

However, some authors have questioned such a direct and linear relationship, such as Oliver (1999), who posits that the link between these two variables is far from being well specified and that it would be more appropriate to consider the intervention of mediating variables. Customer satisfaction is a necessary but insufficient condition for ensuring customer loyalty (Neal, 1999). Following the above line of ideas, Ngobo (1998) has empirically validated this non-linearity in his discussion of the existence of two critical satisfaction thresholds: a minimum threshold at which loyalty behaviors are significantly related to satisfaction, and a maximum threshold beyond which loyalty tends to decline. Moreover, a significant number of researchers have emphasized that relational quality is a pillar of consumer loyalty formation and the development of long-term relationships, as well as the strengthening of their resistance to competitive offers (Crosby et al., 1990; Bejou et al., 1996; Macintosh and Lockshin, 1997; Walsh et al., 2010). Thus, relation quality linking satisfaction and loyalty by involving the mediation of certain facets of relation quality is a cross-cutting model inherent in many contexts, but one that is particularly important in the buyer-seller relationship in B2C (Garbarino and Johnson, 1999; De Wulf et al., 2001; Palmatier et al., 2006; Hsu et al., 2024).

III. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Drawing on the multidimensional concept of relational quality and the interrelationship between its various facets (Crosby et al., 1990; Roberts et al., 2003; Lages et al., 2005; Rauyruen and Miller, 2007), this paper will highlight these relationships by linking them to satisfaction and loyalty, with a view to proposing a specific “relational chain” for B2C buyer-seller relationships.

III.I. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND TRUST

The link between trust and satisfaction remains problematic, even though they are considered two key concepts in relationship marketing, and their association has been widely established in various contexts (Morgan and Hunt, 1994). Several researchers consider that trust determines satisfaction, such as Anderson and Narus (1990), who showed that customer trust in their trading partner reduces conflict and promotes satisfaction. Other researchers, however, consider satisfaction to be a determinant of trust (Dwyer et al., 1987; Crosby et al., 1990; Ganeason, 1994). For example, in consumer behavior, satisfaction with a brand or retailer is a major asset for establishing and developing a relationship of trust (Frisou, 1998; Siriex and Dubois, 1999). Cumulative experiences provide reassurance, minimizing feelings of uncertainty and vulnerability (Kaabachi, 2007). This dynamic was also highlighted by Crosby et al. (1990) in interpersonal service relationships. Yum and Kim (2024) recently confirm this relationship in the digital environment, particularly when the experience has a personal or human aspect.

In business-to-business sales, customer satisfaction helps build trust in the supplier (Selnes, 1993). So, in line with previous studies, it's common to assume that the buyer's overall satisfaction with the seller boosts their trust. This leads us to the following hypothesis:

H2: Buyer's satisfaction in their relationship with the seller positively influences their trust in the seller.

III.II. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SATISFACTION AND PERCEIVED UTILITY VALUE OF THE RELATIONSHIP

Several researchers consider that perceived value leads to consumer satisfaction in the context of consumer behavior (Babin et al., 1994). This perspective holds that satisfaction is the immediate result of the consumer's comparison between expected value and actual perceived value. Nevertheless, adopting a more relational perspective, other researchers consider that satisfaction could determine perceived value rather than result from it. According to them, “value is not just the result of a calculation, it is the product of an experience” (Filser, 2000, p.2). It stems logically from the buyer's cumulative satisfaction with their experiences and is “not found in the product purchased, the brand chosen, or the object owned” (Holbrook, 1999, p.8).

Some researchers, such as Neal (1999), call for the incorporation of perceived value as a mediating variable between satisfaction

and loyalty, stating that satisfaction, despite its appeal, does not automatically guarantee consumer loyalty and that its contribution is reinforced by perceived value. Blut et al's (2024) meta-analysis confirms this relationship, particularly in situations where the purchase decision involves difficulty or uncertainty. Thus, through their cumulative interactions with their trading partner, satisfied buyers interpret the effectiveness and practical usefulness of the relationship positively (risk reduction, time savings, relevance of recommendations, etc.). We therefore formulate the following hypothesis:

H3: The buyer's satisfaction with their relationship with the salesperson has a positive influence on their perceived utility value of the relationship.

III.III. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TRUST AND THE UTILITARIAN VALUE OF THE RELATIONSHIP

Researchers disagree about the link between trust and the utilitarian value of the relationship. Some researchers believe that trust depends on the benefits of the relationship in different contexts (Ulaga et al., 2006; Monfort et al., 2025). For example, Moliner (2009) showed that, in the service area, the perceived functional value of a hospital has an impact on trust in its honesty and benevolence.

Other researchers, however, argue that trust creates value for the buyer by empirically validating the mediating role of relationship value in the link between trust and commitment (Garbarino and Johnson, 1999) or trust and loyalty (Sirdeshmukh et al., 2002). They state that developing a relationship with a competent provider who is inclined to look after the buyer's interests produces both utilitarian and psychological benefits for the buyer, such as reduced risk. Comfort and security make the relationship seem more efficient, which makes buying easier and reduces uncertainty and related cognitive costs (Kaabachi, 2007).

In the same consumer behavior context, trust in the brand is based on reciprocity and reliability standards, which in turn reduce the risk and uncertainty perceived by the consumer (Gwinner, 1998). Raval and Grönroos (1996) showed that, in the context of sales, supplier security and credibility reduce the costs perceived by the customer, thereby improving the perceived value of the relationship. For their part, Alesiana and Ferrera (2002) postulate that when people trust each other, transaction costs tend to decrease and organizations function better. Thus, by analogy with the studies presented above, we assume that trust in the seller's honesty and benevolence creates benefits for the buyer (particularly of a utilitarian nature) arising from their relationship with their exchange partner. We therefore state that:

H4: The buyer's trust in their exchange partner positively affects their perceived Utilitarian value of the relationship.

III.IV. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE UTILITARIAN VALUE OF THE RELATIONSHIP AND EMOTIONAL COMMITMENT

Buyers' commitment to a relationship with their partner is mainly motivated by their interests and objectives (Allen and Meyer, 1990). Indeed, this relational disposition may depend on several economic, social, and psychological factors (Bagozzi, 1995; Sheth and Parvatiyar, 1995).

Since we have mainly focused on the economic aspect of relationship value, we have concentrated more on the economic motives that encourage buyer commitment to their co-exchange. Some authors (Dwyer et al., 1987; Morgan and Hunt, 1994) argue that the benefits of the relationship (reduction in costs and uncertainty) encourage the establishment and maintenance of a strong relationship with an exchange partner. In a study of the quality of the relationship between tourists and travel agencies, Moliner et al. (2007) proved that the functional value of the tourist package determines the tourist's commitment to the agency through satisfaction. In this vein, some authors (Blois, 1996) emphasize that buyer commitment results from their assessment of their relationship with their partner, comparing the benefits they receive with those offered by competitors. Similarly, Kaabachi (2007) highlighted a positive association between the two facets of relational value (utilitarian value and affective value) and consumer commitment to the brand.

Proposing a dynamic model dealing with the evolution of consumers' evaluations and attitudes towards the brand overtime, Johnson et al. (2006) highlighted the mediating role of affective commitment and perceived ethics in the relationship between perceived value (cognitive in nature) and behavioral intentions at an advanced stage of the relationship. In fact, it appears that the perception of the cognitive value of the relationship with the brand determines the consumer's future behavioral intentions at an early stage of the relationship. However, as experience with the brand accumulates, it is rather the affective attitude towards it that determines behavioral intentions, which corroborates attitude theory (Stoetzel, 1941). Other studies, like Blut's (2024), have demonstrated that utility value impacts commitment, particularly when the buyer is seeking functional benefits and reliability. Hence:

H5: The relationship's perceived utility value positively influences the buyer's emotional commitment to the seller.

III.V. THE MEDIATING ROLE OF EMOTIONAL COMMITMENT IN THE SATISFACTION-LOYALTY RELATIONSHIP

Commitment does not reflect buyer loyalty but rather constitutes a precursor to it and acts as a mediator in the satisfaction-loyalty relationship (Kaur & Soch, 2018). Indeed, it serves to predict consumer behavioral intentions (Morgan & Hunt, 1994; Hennig-Thurau & Klee, 1997; Garbarino and Johnson, 1999), particularly in interpersonal relationships (Palmatier et al., 2006). An engaged customer is not only willing to maintain their relationship with the seller (Geyskens et al., 1996), but also to exhibit loyal behaviors such as repurchase, recommendation, and resistance to competitive solicitations, which in turn constitute an important facet of loyalty (Dick and Basu, 1994; Pritchard et al., 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2002). Several studies in the financial services field have confirmed that when customers feel a strong connection to their bank or service provider, this has a positive impact on their loyalty (Boateng and Narteh, 2016; Farooq and Moon, 2020; Khraiwish et al., 2022). In view of this analysis, we state the following:

H6: Buyers' emotional commitment to sellers positively influences their loyalty.

In the light of these causal links spontaneously put forward by the respondents and reinforced by previous work in various marketing contexts, we have arrived at an arrangement of the various relational variables analyzed in a relational chain that looks like this:

Figure 1: The specific relational chain for the buyer-seller relationship in the B2C context

IV. METHODOLOGY

To test the research model, we adopted an empirical approach based on a questionnaire survey. Before collecting the data, we specified the various measures and designed the data collection procedures.

IV.I. SCALE OF MEASUREMENT

The choice of measurement instruments was based on their suitability for the study context and their psychometric qualities in previous research. The various measures used are summarized in Appendix 2. We felt it appropriate to control certain factors that could affect the variables studied. As well as factors relating to the buyer (age, gender, educational level, involvement in the product category), we are keen to control for a dyadic feature, the length of the relationship.

IV.II. DATA COLLECTION

We conducted face-to-face surveys with buyers to collect data. We focused particularly on retail sales, while opting for a multi-sector study. Given that we operate in a relational sales environment, our focus was limited to sectors where products are purchased after careful consideration, to ensure a minimum duration of interaction between sales staff and buyers, as well as a minimum level of involvement on the part of the buyers surveyed (sales of computer equipment, furniture, household electrical equipment, building materials, automobile equipments, etc.).

In the interests of quality control, we applied a series of checks (Akrouf, 2010). As a result of this process, we selected a sample of 135 buyers.

V. FINDINGS

The data collected underwent two analyses: an exploratory factor analysis to evaluate the factor structure of the measurement instruments and a confirmatory factor analysis to test the measurement and structure models.

V.I. EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS

All the data revealed satisfactory values for the KMO indices and Bartlett's sphericity test, reflecting their factorizability. Principal component analysis with Oblimin rotation allowed us to ensure the stability of the measurement instruments selected. The various measurements generally show good psychometric qualities, as shown in the table below:

Table 1 : Measures' psychometric qualities

	Factor number	Variable descriptions	Eigenvalue	% of variance explained
Satisfaction	1	SATISFACTION	3,147	62,935
Loyalty	1	LOYALTY	5,710	74,352
Relationship quality	3	Relationship utilitarian value RUV)	8,834	77,893
		TRUST	1,048	
		Emotional commitment (EC)	0,844	

V.II. MEASUREMENT MODEL ASSESSMENT

Results for the constructs studied will be summarized according to the following criteria: the first eigenvalue and Cronbach's alpha coefficient to analyze the unidimensionality and internal consistency of each construct; Dillon-Goldstein's Rho to test composite reliability; average extracted variances (AEV) and cross loadings for convergent and discriminant validity.

First-order construct analysis: The various validation analyses of the first-order model constructs indicate that they are reliable, with indices above 0.8. Moreover, all manifest variables related to the constructs have correlation coefficients above 0.7,

satisfactory cross loadings, and VME values exceeding 0.627, confirming their convergent validity. The discriminant validity of these constructs is also confirmed, as they each have a VME higher than the square of the correlations of the other latent variables.

Second-order construct analysis: We considered it appropriate to verify whether the second-order construct (relational quality) is significantly reflected by the related first-order constructs. To do this, we adopted the hierarchical modeling approach (Mackenz et al., 2005). Results from this analysis show that the partial measurement model has a good fit. The first-order constructs reflect the multidimensional construct of relational quality. Their contributions to the latter are highly significant. The reliability indicator values are acceptable, leading us to conclude that the construct is reliable. The convergent validity is also confirmed by the VME indicator.

convergent validity: Analysis of cross-loadings enabled us to verify that the manifest variables relating to each latent variable do not contribute significantly to the formation of other latent variables. Furthermore, the variance captured by all constructs (VME) is good. We can therefore confirm the convergent validity of the constructs.

Discriminant validity: we note that the correlations between the constructs are less than the square root of the average variance extracted for each construct, which demonstrates the discriminant validity of the constructs studied.

Evaluation of the overall model fit: The GOF is around 0.550 and is close to its Bootstrap estimate, indicating the stability of the model. In addition, the index of the relative GOF and those corresponding to the measurement model and the structural model are high and stable, reflecting a good quality of model fit to the empirical data.

V.III. STRUCTURAL MODEL ASSESSMENT

This involves R² and path coefficient analysis, as shown in Appendix 3. The analysis reveals that, overall, the variables studied are well explained by the model: The R² of 0.609 shows that the utility value of the relationship is well explained, as are trust (0.608) and emotional commitment (0.559). Moreover, based on the analysis of the path coefficients relating to the latent variables and their level of significance, we note that they are generally acceptable. To further evaluate the model, we conducted cross-validation using the blindfolding approach based on cv-communality and cv-redundancy indices (Tenenhaus et al., 2005). The results of this analysis are generally acceptable. In addition, the GoF analysis of the internal model, which is very high (0.921), also attests to the model's good fit to the data. We supplemented this analysis with an analysis of Stone-Geisser's Q² coefficients. These indices are generally positive and therefore satisfactory.

Based on these analyses of the structure model, we can conclude that it fits well. The path coefficient values are significant and generally acceptable, as shown in the table below.

Table 2 : Hypotheses testing

	Hypotheses	Path coefficient	Lower bound	Upper bound	Decision
H2	SATISFACTION → TRUST	0,312	0,266	0,346	Confirmed
H3	SATISFACTION → RELATIONSHIP UTILITARIAN VALUE	0,264	0,225	0,297	Confirmed
H4	TRUST → RELATIONSHIP UTILITARIAN VALUE (RUV)	0,260	0,222	0,289	Confirmed
H5	RELATIONSHIP UTILITARIAN VALUE → EMOTIONAL COMMITMENT (EC)	0,278	0,228	0,318	Confirmed
H6	EMOTIONAL COMMITMENT → LOYALTY	0,301	0,257	0,342	Confirmed

V.IV. MEDIATOR EFFECTS TEST

The XLSTAT tool enabled us to conduct an analysis of indirect effects, the significant nature of which was verified using the Bootstrap method. The various indirect effects considered are summarized in the table below:

Table 3: Direct and indirect effects

Effect of on	SATIS		TRUST		RUV		EC		LOYALTY	
	Direct Effets	Indirect Effets								
SATIS			0,312		0,264	0,081*	0,000	0,096*		0,029*
TRUST					0,260	0,000	0,000	0,072*		0,022*
RUV							0,278	0,000		0,084*

* : significant

** : Any effects related to ethical behavior are negative, as this variable is reflected by items with an inverted score.

Based on the data in the table above, we can draw further conclusions about the causal chain between the various variables in the proposed relational chain incorporating the facets of relational quality. Indeed, the indirect effect of satisfaction on the utilitarian value of the relationship is significant, highlighting the mediating role of trust. Such mediation is partial, given that the direct influence of satisfaction on perceived value is validated.

Moreover, the indirect effect of trust on emotional commitment is significantly different from 0, hence the mediating role of utility value in this relationship. Finally, the indirect effect of the perceived value of the relationship on relational loyalty allows us to comment on the mediating role of the effect of emotional commitment. It should therefore be noted that customer satisfaction is not sufficient to guarantee customer loyalty. Instead, it seems to trigger a quality relationship that leads customers to develop an intention to return to the same seller for future purchases and to recommend them to their friends and family.

VI. DISCUSSION

In the following section, we first discuss the concept of relational quality specific to the context under study (B-to-C) derived from the exploratory qualitative study. Then, we discuss the relational sequence specific to the buyer-seller dyad that we have just proposed.

VI.I. RELATIONAL QUALITY CONCEPTUALIZATION

In terms of relational quality conceptualization, the results show its multidimensionality, which confirms the first hypothesis stated. The most prominent facets mentioned by respondents were buyer trust and commitment to their trading partner (see Appendix1). These are social in nature (De Burca et al., 2004; Woo & Ennew, 2004; Holmlund, 2008) and have been widely adopted by researchers in various contexts, particularly in the B2C field (Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Vesel & Zabkar, 2010). This concept also incorporates the utilitarian value of the relationship, which refers to the economic aspect of the relationship. This brings us closer to certain hybrid conceptualizations (De Burca et al., 2004; Huntley, 2006; Holmlund, 2008). However, our results do not seem to be consistent with other research (Ulaga & Eggert, 2006), where utilitarian value appears to be a determinant of relationship quality.

Even more, trust was mainly modeled by the affective dimension (trust in the seller's kindness and honesty) in line with the views of some researchers who consider these two dimensions of trust to be the most important indicators of the quality of interpersonal relationships (Crosby et al., 1990; Roberts et al., 2003). In fact, it seems that the assessment of relationship quality revolves around the emotional attachment between the two partners at the expense of its cognitive dimension, which may be explained by the relational orientation of respondents in this sales context (Volle & Mimouni, 2003).

VI.II. THE RELATIONAL SEQUENCE PROPOSED

We were able to empirically validate the significant and positive effect of the buyer's overall satisfaction with their trading partner resulting from their trust in the latter's goodwill and honesty (H2) and the influence of trust on the utilitarian value of the relationship as perceived by the buyer (H4). Trust thus mediates between these two variables. However, this mediation is only partial, as the link between satisfaction and the utilitarian value of the relationship is significant (H3), which is consistent with the academic literature that has inferred the crucial role of relational value in the sales context (Walter et al., 2000). This sequencing seems logical, given that if the buyer is generally satisfied with their relationship with the seller, they will be more inclined to trust them and form a positive impression of the usefulness of the relationship established between them. Moreover, the same mediation effects test procedure revealed the partial mediating role of the utilitarian value of the relationship between trust and emotional commitment to the salesperson. Thus, we find that the more the buyer perceives the importance of the added value of the exchange relationship, the more they will be inclined to develop a certain emotional attachment to their co-exchanger, which reassures them further. This aligns with Kaabachi's (2007) that the buyer's commitment to the relationship can also be motivated by extrinsic factors.

Validating the effect of satisfaction on the utilitarian value of the relationship (H3) and the effect of the latter on emotional commitment (H5) proves that the relationship between satisfaction and emotional commitment is mediated by the utilitarian value of the relationship. So, if the buyer considers their exchange relationship to be satisfactory, they will be inclined to perceive the benefits generated by that relationship, which translates into their affective commitment to their co-exchanger. Thus, the facets of relational quality occupy a central place in this relational chain, which confirms the findings of Palmatier et al. (2006). They emphasize the crucial mediating role of this concept in the context of relationship selling, as it tends to combine the characteristics of the exchange partners, as well as those of the relationship, with the buyer's behavioral intentions. In this way, the buyer not only develops a positive appreciation of their relationship with their partner but is also willing to recommend them to others and to return for future purchases. This aligns with the literature that highlights the seller's determining role in the exchange relationship, stipulating that buyers are more predisposed to loyalty to the seller than to the company (Macintosh & Lockshin, 1997). Moreover, this cumulative sequence aligns with social exchange theory, which posits that customers become loyal when they perceive a range of effective and utilitarian benefits in their relationship with the seller. Furthermore, it should be noted that several causal chains have been proposed in various contexts (Aurier et al., 2001; Kaabachi, 2007; Mornay et al., 2025).

Although the relational chain we have just proposed encompasses most of the variables incorporated by Aurier et al. (2001), it differs in its sequence. Indeed, these authors argue that, in the context studied, the perceived value of the relationship is a precursor to satisfaction and trust in the brand. In contrast, our approach is closer to the relational chain structure proposed by Kaabachi (2007), which distinguishes between the utilitarian and hedonic value of the relationship and considers satisfaction and trust in the store as determinants of relationship value. However, unlike in our case, relational loyalty is not included in this sequence. Furthermore, we note a certain divergence in the conceptualizations of trust and commitment adopted, as we have focused particularly on their affective aspect.

VII. CONCLUSION

This research makes contributions to marketing research from both a theoretical and managerial perspective. Theoretically, this research focuses on the buyer-seller relationship in a context that has been relatively unexplored in previous marketing research, namely the B2C sector. It has led to a clarification of the dimensionality of the quality of the buyer-seller relationship in this context. Combining the respondents' discourse with previous research on relationship selling led us to propose and subsequently validate a "relational chain." This chain illustrates successive causal links between relational variables which, starting from overall (cumulative) satisfaction with the seller, tend to strengthen relational loyalty while fostering the perception of the relationship's utilitarian value, trust, and commitment to the exchange partner. From a managerial perspective, the study supports managers in training and monitoring salespeople and in disseminating a customer-centric culture. Indeed, companies must train their salespeople in interpersonal skills such as active listening, transparency, personalization, reliability, and so on. These skills can also be used as selection criteria during recruitment. Practitioners must also focus on raising awareness among salespeople

about the importance of creating and maintaining good customer relationships by promoting a "customer-centric culture" (Poujol, 2008).

The importance given to both emotional and economic aspects in the exchange relationship highlights the need for salesperson adaptability (Weitz et al., 1986). This ability can be developed in salespeople through role-playing or simulations. Furthermore, the validated relational chain demonstrates the importance that the salesperson must assign to each of these variables according to its weight and triggering role. The results also confirm the importance of commitment in predicting loyalty. Retailers would therefore benefit from developing loyalty programs and implementing satisfaction measures or communication mechanisms (internet, telephone) to ensure customer feedback. The integration of tangible benefits (expert advice, risk reduction, simplified choice) can also be offered to customers, given the attractive utilitarian value of the relationship.

This study has some limitations, notably the small sample size, which hinders the generalization of the results. Furthermore, the one-off survey adopted argues in favour of a longitudinal approach considering the dynamic aspect of the relational variables studied (Moliner et al, 2007).

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Frequency of occurrence of dimensions of relational quality

Relationship quality dimensions	Cumulative frequency	
	Absolute	Relative
Relationship utilitarian value	20	18.2%
Emotional Commitment	39	35.4 %
Trust in the seller's goodwill and honesty	51	46.4 %
Totals	110	100 %

Appendix 2: Measures adopted

Model	Measurement
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Constructs	
Satisfaction with the seller	Ramsey & Sohi (1997)
The relationship utilitarian value	Kaabachi (2007)
Trust in the seller	Adapted from Ramsey & Sohi (1997); Ganesan (1994)
The buyer's emotional commitment	Adapted from Cater & Cater (2010) ; Lacoeuilhe (2000) ; Roberts et al. (2003)
Loyalty to the seller	Adapted from Boyer & Nefzi (2008)

Appendix 3 : Structural model assessment

Latent variables	Type	Average scores (manifest variable)	R ²	adjusted R ²	Communalities & Average Variance Extraction (AVE)	Means	DG-rho.
SATIS	Endogenous	0,000	0,468	0,451	0,826	0,386	0,934
Trust	Endogenous	0,000	0,608	0,589	0,721	0,438	0,928
RUV	Endogenous	0,000	0,609	0,590	0,800	0,487	0,923
EC	Endogenous	0,000	0,559	0,531	0,811	0,453	0,955
LOYALTY	Endogenous	0,000	0,594	0,575	0,766	0,455	0,958
Means			0,338		0,696	0,269	